

Machine actionable metadata models

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Code and data availability statement

FAIR and machine actionable reporting guidelines:

- <https://github.com/FAIRsharing/mircat>

Code:

- <http://github.com/fairsharing/jsonldschema>
- <https://github.com/fairsharing/jsonschema-documenter>
- <https://github.com/FAIRsharing/JSONschema-compare-and-view>

Documentation:

- <https://jsonldschema.readthedocs.io>

Abstract

Community-developed minimum information checklists are designed to drive the rich and consistent reporting of metadata, underpinning the reproducibility and reuse of the data. These reporting guidelines, however, are usually narrative in form as intended for human consumption. Machine-readable versions are also needed. Firstly, to provide the necessary quantitative and verifiable measures of the degree to which the metadata descriptors meet these community requirements, a requirement of the FAIR Principles. Secondly, to encourage the creation of standards-driven templates for metadata authoring, especially when describing complex experiments that require multiple reporting guidelines to be used in combination or extended.

We present our approach to the creation of machine-readable models, and our open source toolkit. We apply the approach to an exemplar set of reporting guidelines in Life Science

and discuss the challenges. Our work, targeted to developers of standards and tools and others who are familiar with standards, promotes the concept of compositional metadata elements and encourages the creation of community-standards which are modular and interoperable from the onset.

Introduction

The publication and release of data and methods holds the potential of providing new research insights and justifies establishing domain specific data repositories. Data that are routinely available in a transparent and persistent manner to support peer-review and withstand reproducibility can effectively drive science forward. This is especially true in the area of agent-driven knowledge discovery from data. However, considerable efforts are still required to discover, harvest, clean and harmonise datasets in order to obtain data corpora suitable for consumption by software and learning systems. A key element for these operations is the availability of machine-readable metadata, i.e. descriptive data about the data, which provides the contextual information essential to interpret and reuse the data. In the Life Sciences, for example, the metadata about molecular entities of interest (e.g., metabolites, proteins) and the experimental steps (e.g., provenance of study materials, measurement and technology types) are pivotal information to ensure that shared investigations are comprehensible, data reusable, and work, in principle, reproducible.

Metadata, a pillar of FAIR

Along with unique and persistent identifiers, metadata is a pillar of the FAIR Principles, guiding scientific data management and stewardship¹. The principles promote the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of data, including digital assets such as datasets, algorithms and models, emphasising the need for machine-readability of the data. Widely endorsed by communities in the academic² and private sectors³, as well as infrastructure providers, scholarly publishers, funders and other global organizations^{4,5}, FAIR has quickly become a fundamental enabler of digital transformation.

Currently, two major challenges to putting FAIR in action are to guide researchers to provide richly described metadata (metadata authoring), and evaluate the level of FAIRness of a given dataset or any other digital object⁶ (FAIR assessment). Both processes require that the metadata provided is sufficiently rich, and that it complies with the relevant community-defined reporting standards. For tools and automated systems to assist with metadata authoring and related assessment we need canonical and machine-actionable profiles of these reporting standards against which to create or measure the level of metadata description.

Metadata standards, values and challenges

Since the early 2000s, a growing number of community-based standardisation initiatives have worked to harmonise the reporting and sharing of the metadata of datasets, and recently also of software code and other digital objects. In the Life Sciences over a thousand metadata standards have been created and/or implemented by several thousand data repositories, which are now discoverable in FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/standards>). These community-driven efforts encompass: minimum information checklists or reporting guidelines; terminology artifacts or semantics, ranging from dictionaries to ontologies; models and formats or syntax. Reporting guidelines play a pivotal role, because they define the metadata the community sees as the necessary and sufficient information that must be reported to contextualize and understand datasets. These reporting guidelines, however, are intended for human consumption and are usually in narrative form and therefore prone to interpretation ambiguities, making automatic validation and compliance against metadata standards a difficult and approximate task. The reporting guidelines serve as an initial phase that facilitate the development of models and formats, defining the formal structures and relationships of information to be reported along with transmission formats to facilitate data exchange. These models and formats often require the use of one or more terminologies, which provide definitions and univocal identification for concepts.

The uptake of these metadata standards by the research community, data repositories, tools developers, services providers, and policy makers has been slow and uneven, mainly because of a lack of incentives and information, but also due to real technical challenges. However, the community mobilization around FAIR-enabling tools and services, and the network effect of resources like FAIRsharing ⁷, are bringing a renewed energy and attention to these issues. In the following sections, we summarize the two key challenges with using the metadata standards, which are the motivation for our work.

Interpretation and fragmentation

From any of the reporting guidelines expressed as narratives, more than one model/format may be created, with different interpretations of the metadata requirements. Although not ideal, unfortunately this is often a common scenario, which defeats the original purpose of having a common metadata representation to facilitate exchange and sharing of the information across systems⁸. Therefore, it is quite common to see various interpretations of the same reporting guideline as different implementations in databases⁹; an example is illustrated in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. (A) GEO (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.5hc8vt>) and ArrayExpress (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.6k0kwd>) are two databases highly recommended by journals and funders data policies, and both implement the community-defined MIAME reporting guideline to describe microarray experiment (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.32b10v>), among others. The implementation of MIAME is done via several formats (used to upload and download datasets from these two databases), which include SOFT (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3qxr9>) and MINiML (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.gaegy8>) for GEO; MAGE-ML (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.x964fb>) that is now deprecated and superseded by MAGE-TAB (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.ak8p5g>) for the ArrayExpress, which also uses the EFO terminology (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.1qr4tz>) to annotate the metadata. (B) Using a few metadata requirements from MIAME as example (namely: study, study title, study description) we illustrate how the metadata labels, along with their level of requirement (must, should, may), varies across the formats used by the two databases.

The wealth of domain-specific metadata standards is proof that communities operate within their domains of interest and expertise, and these activities should be encouraged. However, the vast majority of community-focused activities creates fragmentation that leads to a lack of interoperability amongst the resulting standards. This is a major issue when a dataset to be described cuts across the boundaries of these communities. For example, the description of an experiment where the subjects are characterised with various analytical methods, using different technologies (e.g., protein-protein interaction assays, genomic sequencing, metabolite concentrations and proteomics) is particularly challenging from the standards-compliance point of view.

These challenges with different interpretations and the fragmentation of the reporting standards impact on their use and adoption. It becomes harder for researchers to understand how to comply with these requirements; for curators, data managers and developers, who may have more familiarity with the metadata standards, to cater for all types of experiments (produced by the researchers they support); and for anybody who wants to carry out a FAIR assessment, to measure the level of compliance of data against the relevant metadata standards. Creating

templates, forms or developing generic metadata authoring tools, which aim to comply with all possible combinations of reporting standards, is quite difficult. It easily leads to a combinatorial explosion of options, and can result in complex tools that may discourage researchers rather than incentivise them to report richly described metadata. The question is: how can we streamline and automate this combinatorial process, minimizing the manual input and error rate, and provide a common method that third-party tools can use?

The need for modular, reusable, metadata elements

We have first-hand experience with these challenges, in the form of the results of our long-standing collaborations with researchers, curators, data managers and developers, as well as standardization efforts and policy makers via our ISA Commons ¹⁰, the FAIRsharing and (previously) the MIBBI ¹¹ communities. Our experience suggests that metadata authoring templates should be pieced together from smaller elements, taking into consideration the type of the sample, the experimental condition, the technology employed and so on. We know that the best metadata standards are invisible to the researchers. Therefore, the ISA Commons community has configured many templates manually, using a dedicated component of our ISA software suite ¹²; we have created a library of standards-compliant configurations that enable deposition to specific data repositories. These configurations are in XML format and require maintenance; specifically, they must be revised when a standard is updated or modified, which is quite common especially for new and emerging technologies.

Recently, the need for the reuse of machine-actionable metadata has also been the subject of Metadata for Machine workshops¹³, and a series of workshops, co-organized by GO-FAIR and the Research Data Alliance (RDA), to which we have also contributed. However, discussions and pilot work to date have been discipline agnostic, and entirely generic, and not yet tested in a real case scenario.

Results

To address these challenges, we focused on a selected subset of reporting guidelines in Life Science, described in **Table 1**. We worked to improve the process, researching new methods to create standards-derived metadata elements that are machine-actionable, modular, and reusable for composition in intelligent authoring templates, tools, validation and assessment tools at scale. We present our concept of ‘atomic’ metadata elements, and an architecture that encourages reuse and modularity based on JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) technologies and

a set of open source tools, which can be used to explore, create, extend and validate these metadata models. We apply our method to a set of reporting guidelines to illustrate how to create a machine-readable reporting guideline *de novo*, and how to merge two existing guidelines into a new set of schemas.

Reporting guideline name	Domain coverage	Format	Date of creation	FAIRsharing record DOI
MIAME	Transcriptomics	Textual, PDF file	1999	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.32b10v
MIACA	Cellular assay	XSD	2006	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.7d0yv9
MIFlowcyt	Flow cytometry	Textual, PDF file	2007	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.kcnjj2
MINSEQE	High-throughput nucleotide sequencing	Textual, PDF file	2008	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.a55z32
MIXS-MIMARKS	Nucleotide sequencing from environmental samples	Excel, XML file	2011	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.zvrep1
MIACME	Cell migration assay	generate <i>ab initio</i> as JSON Schema	2016	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.vh2ye1
MIAPPE	Plant phenotyping	Excel, TSV file	2018	https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.nd9ce9

Table 1: The set of reporting guidelines we selected to illustrate our approach. These encompassed examples in narrative and formalized format, older and newer work, and include some that have a domain overlap in order to test the composability capability.

The concept of atomic metadata elements

The concept of ‘atomic’ metadata elements address the need for modularity that retains the provenance information about the reporting requirements they are derived from, as illustrated in **Figure 2**. The metadata elements would need to be represented to capture conditions and dependencies between relevant elements. For example, in the MIACME reporting guidelines requirement about cell migration experiments (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.vh2ye1>) for an ‘experiment type’ that is *in vitro*, information about the ‘growth medium’ must be provided. These conditions and dependencies can drive the creation of smarter and faster authoring templates, tools, validation and assessment tools, if we are to make the most of these community standards in the description and validation of metadata. The machine-actionability and the

modularity of the reporting guidelines will allow the automated creation for the model/format based on its representation, and enable syntactic and semantic comparison among community requirements. The latter will assist with the identification of common metadata elements, to integrate and merge existing reporting standards (or part of them) or create a new one. Ultimately, this modularity will also foster reuse and maximize interoperability across these fragmented community efforts.

Figure 2. The SRA database (<https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.g7t2hv>) requires metadata descriptors to comply to MINSEQE reporting guidelines for high-throughput sequencing data and, if the sample is of environmental origin, also to MixS-MIMARKS requirements. We use this example to illustrate the decomposition of these community-developed metadata requirements, to identify common and unique elements and mark their provenance.

Building machine-actionable metadata models

Target users, use cases and technology

Our work is targeted at standards developers, and others who have familiarity with the metadata standards, or develop metadata authoring and FAIR assessment tools to help researchers to describe increasingly complex experiments and complying to more than one community-defined reporting requirements. The two main use cases (UC) that have guided our work:

- UC1: how to create a reporting guideline that is machine-readable *ab initio*.
- UC2: how to merge two existing guidelines into a new set of schemas.

The second use case addresses the need to ensure compatibility, detect overlaps and deal with redundant requirements, while retaining unique metadata descriptors.

To express metadata requirements from existing reporting guidelines, we relied on JSON, a quasi *de facto* standard for development web oriented components and services. Specifically, we used JSON and JSON Schema technologies (<https://json-schema.org>), in order to decouple the annotation requirements from a domain model. JSON Schema is a vocabulary to validate JSON files, and JSON-LD (<http://json-ld.org>) is an extension of JSON to support linked data: a way to create a machine-readable and standard way to share data on the web.

To store and provide access to the machine-actionable metadata models, we have set up MIRcat, the Minimum Information Requirement catalogue (<https://github.com/FAIRsharing/mircat>) in GitHub. MIRcat contains JSON Schema representations and the ancillary JSON-LD context files for the efforts listed in **Table 1**. In this way, the validation of the reporting requirements can be done by software agents either against the JSON Schemas or the JSON instance documents. To demonstrate the approach, we used FlowRepository (<http://flowrepository.org/>), an archive of Flow Cytometry data, as a test bed. Using the MIflowCyt specification documentation, we created a set of JSON Schemas (<https://github.com/FAIRsharing/mircat/tree/master/miflowcyt>). Retrieving experiments metadata, the XML instances were transformed into JSON and the linked data attributes were injected to obtain the final JSON-LD instances that were then validated against the JSON Schema set. The aim of this work was twofold: to demonstrate feasibility of the JSON schema based approach, which also acted as a technology update for MIflowCyt and to provide a baseline for following work, demonstrating the ability to perform validation and LD injection.

Annotate, explore and validate

JSON-ScheeLD is a tool that facilitates the binding of schema elements to semantic terms pulled from ontologies and helps manage complex sets of JSON Schemas. The tool assists users in creating JSON-LD ontology-specific context file stubs as well as “mappings files” between contexts and their corresponding schemas. The remaining task for the user is the identification of ontology terms and identifiers to map to each entity. The mapping files allow the creation of as many contexts as needed. This high modularity offers the ability for distinct communities to use the same schemas but annotated with different terms and/or vocabulary fitting their respective requirements.

The production of JSON Schemas often lacks in terms of visualisation support, hampering interactions between end-users and developers. A number of rendering tools exist but they have either limited capabilities (e.g. failure to resolve complex schemas or to account for context files) or tied to large frameworks (e.g. cloudflare, <https://www.cloudflare.com>). To help users visualize JSON Schemas' models, we created the JSON Schema *Documenter*, a lightweight AngularJS-

based client-side web application which presents *in-situ* the associated semantic markup extracted from the JSON-LD context files. **Figure 3** illustrates the process required to create a new reporting guideline in a machine-readable form.

Figure 3: How to create a reporting guideline that is machine-readable *ab initio*

1) The developer manually creates the JSON schemas to represent the reporting guideline. 2) Optional step: *JSON ScheeLD* assists the developer by providing a mean to validate the model against the JSON Schema specification; and the *JSON Schema Documenter* helps visualise models in the browser. 3) *JSON ScheeLD* extends the model by creating stubs for each of the ontology-specific context files associated with the schemas. This can also be used to extend an existing reporting guideline. 4) The developer selects each ontology term for each schema field and fill them up in the context file stubs. 5) Optional step: once done, the *JSON Schema Documenter* can be used to verify that the all the fields are correctly described by an ontology term.

Compare and merge

We produced a programmatic way to perform pairwise comparisons of JSON Schemas' models to detect overlaps and commonalities, which could inform modularisation. *JSON ScheeLD* compares the two models by aligning the ontology terms pulled from the context files and creates an output file read by *JSON Compare Viewer* front-end app (<https://github.com/FAIRsharing/JSONschema-compare-and-view>). That same output file is used by the *JSON ScheeLD* merge function to generate a new set of schemas that includes both models it was generated from. We have used this process to merge MIACMA into the MIACA schemas, as shown in **Figure 4**. During this process the provenance of the metadata descriptors from the MIACA reporting guideline was preserved (as previously explained in Figure 2).

Figure 4: How to merge two existing guidelines into a new set of schemas.

1) The developer uses the *JSON Schema Documenter* to explore the different guidelines. 2) *JSON ScheeLD* relies on the context files to compare the two given models and outputs a file readable by the *JSON Compare Viewer*. This allows the developer to see which fields are semantically identical. 3) *JSON ScheeLD* pulls the fields from the MIACME model and injects them into the MIACA if they are missing and creates a whole new set of schemas and context files. Directionality is important: merging MIACME into MIACA will not produce the same result as merging MIACA into MIACME. 4) After the merge is complete, the developer can go back to step 2 and compare the new model with the old one to ensure quality control.

Towards CEDAR compatible schemas

As part of our collaboration with the Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR) ¹⁴, we provided an adapter and conversion mechanism (<https://jsonldschema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/cedar/cedarIndex.html>) to allow the reporting guidelines expressed in pure JSON Schema draft-04 specifications to be posted, loaded and reused by the CEDAR Workbench. The schema specification adopted by CEDAR requires a pre-processing of the native JSON Schemas drafts specifications. Creating templates via the CEDAR Workbench is possible for simplest use-cases, e.g. when a template follows one reporting guideline. However, for complex cases where two or more reporting guidelines need to be considered, our automated approach via our JSON-ScheeLD's API is the best solution.

Discussion

The core of our work consisted in expressing reporting guidelines formally, i.e. moving from free text descriptions to machine actionable formats. This step is time consuming, hard to automate, and it is a manual process that involves domain experts. In the following sections we discuss the four main challenges, which are also areas of future work, and how to mitigate them: (i) the consistency of the semantic markup, (ii) the versioning of the reporting guidelines, (iii) the

ambiguities of JSON Schema, and (iv) the difficulties with comparing at syntactic and semantic level.

Once the formalization was completed, the next step consisted in performing a semantic markup on the JSON Schema attributes. The choice of the semantic resources is dictated by various constraints, and it is important to clearly articulate the selection process of these resources and to document the process for term selection. A simple selection based on 'string match' is insufficient owing to the homonymy issue. For instance, the notion of 'library' in the MINSEQE reporting guideline, which is focused on nucleic acid sequencing, differs significantly from the one in the MIACA reporting guideline, where 'library' refers to a collection of perturbation agents such as silencing RNA clones. Therefore, beyond the term label, it is essential to consider key metadata of an ontology class ¹⁵, such as definition, synonyms and examples. Documenting term selection, during the semantic markup, is an important process especially when a number of experts are involved in the process. The semantic markup is particularly important as the *JSON ScheeLD Compare* feature uses the compact URIs found in the JSON-LD context file to match elements and decide whether to merge attributes or not. It should be noted that the *JSON ScheeLD Merge* feature does not evaluate ontology classes based on more advanced heuristics, such as calculating semantic similarity distances.

When working with community-defined reporting guidelines one must be aware that these can evolve and new versions be developed. In this case the related schema will need to be updated and changes may break pre-existing compliance. To mitigate this issue a versioning mechanism should be put in place; all versions should remain accessible through a stable and persistent URL, also to avoid breaking objects depending on these schemas. Therefore, schemas themselves need to be FAIR. We will look into organizing the various reporting requirement release versions under the MIRcat repository and around w3id folders holding the different releases. As part of future work, we plan to ensure that the JSON-ScheeLD tool is able to deal with multiple versions of a reporting requirement.

Further enhancements are needed to refine the expression of the constraints under JSON Schema. JSON Schema specifications since draft 3.0 define keywords to allow schema reuse and referencing, thus allowing the creation of more advanced sets of schemas. However, the process of injecting semantic types into JSON instance files using JSON-LD context files, in a programmatic and dynamic way, has limitations. The difficulty is to systematically assign the correct JSON `@type` context when schemas rely on multiple types. Furthermore, we also discovered that the 'anyOf' and 'allOf' keywords can reference multiple schemas, providing contradictory constraints. Unfortunately, the JSON Schema specification does not mention the existence of such cases, therefore the validators do not account for such errors and will not catch these contradictions. As result, it has been our responsibility to produce unambiguous JSON Schema documents.

The technology we used to formally express the reporting guidelines relies on the separation of roles between the syntactic layer (provides the physical constraints of an object) and the semantic one (provides ontology annotation to these constraints). In order to compare two sets of schemas, one should select over which layer one wishes to process. The syntactic comparison relies on the *DeepDiff* python library, and the semantic one on our custom *SemDiff* comparator. However, at this stage they cannot be combined. When considering both layers at the same time, the following questions remain unanswered. Which layer has the highest propriety? Are both layers equally important? How would one weigh these attributes? When two fields have the same semantic annotation but different physical constraints, which field should be prioritized, and how can an instance be compatible with several models that implement contradictory constraints? At this moment, each individual use case should implement their own weighting system if they want to realize combined syntactic and semantic comparisons.

Beside the technical challenges described above, our prototype work demonstrates that the concepts of machine-readable guidelines and compositional metadata elements are achievable. Following common procedures for collaborative open-source software development, we encourage feedback and contributions from developers interested to explore the tools, the schemas and the compositional metadata elements produced to date. While most machine-readable guidelines can be achieved with a high level of confidence and accuracy, some work requires vetting by the original developers of the reporting guidelines. To facilitate this, we plan to link the community-defined reporting guidelines in FAIRsharing with their respective machine-readable models in the MIRcat repository. The ideal scenario is one where reporting guidelines are no longer developed as unstructured narrative, but are expressed with sufficient level of formalization to enable validation by machines. Future work included exploring connections and coordination with other approaches, such LinkML (<https://github.com/linkml>), which aims are providing substantive tooling to support machine readable specifications, the GA4GH schema blocks activities (<https://ga4gh-schemablocks.github.io>), and Human Cell Atlas schema definitions^{16,17} that formally spell out annotation requirements. The long term goal is to develop a consistent and coordinated approach to machine-readable profiles. Formally-defined reporting requirements, with semantic markup, cardinality information, and value-set definitions can also be used to bootstrap the creation of project-specific metadata profiles, possibly with the assistance of software agents powered by models trained on these.

We will also continue to foster a community-wide discussion via our participation in international initiatives on metadata authoring and FAIR assessment, including the Metadata for Machine workshops (by GO-FAIR and RDA, and where CEDAR and FAIRsharing are also part of), and communities actives in international data infrastructures such as ELIXIR (where the ISA toolkit is one of the recommended resources, <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability/rirs>). The need for coordination among community

standards and their interoperability are not trivial issues ¹⁸. There are social and technical challenges. Nevertheless, it is pivotal to foster convergence, modularity and interoperability among the community-standards if we are to realise the vision of FAIR data.

Methods

To demonstrate the feasibility of the approach, we used the subset of reporting guidelines described in **Table 1**. The following criteria were used for the selection: 1) at least one narrative reporting guideline (to assess the extraction from textual representation), 2) at least one formalized reporting guideline (to assess the extraction from formal representation) and 3) a domain overlap in at least one component (to test composability capability). For the latter criteria, we included MIACA and MIACME, which cover cellular systems, and MINSEQE and MIXS-, MIMARKS which cover nucleic acid sequencing.

The reporting guidelines differ in terms of scope as well as development and maturity stages. They also range from purely narrative artefacts (with possible ambiguous definitions) to fully formalized models, which are supported by a model based representation either in the form of a UML diagram, XML schema, JSON schema or Resource Description Framework (RDF) representation. For the reporting guidelines with a formal representation and interpretation and formalisation step was performed independently by two domain experts, and reconciled by a third expert. The task consisted in identifying key concepts (as defined by the authors of the reporting guideline) and building an entity/relationship model from the textual definition. Finally, for each of the identified entities, a concept identifier from a selected ontology was linked to it.

The process, referred to as metadata atomization and markup, relies on the identification and consistent use of semantic resources. We selected schema.org (<https://schema.org>) and OBO Foundry ¹⁹ resources as they provide two distinct and complementary functions. The former is orientated towards data discovery and findability, and the latter focuses on the coherent representations of the biological domains, which are under-represented in schema.org. The metadata atomization and markup is primarily a manual process and hard to automate. To help with the task, we relied on Google Spreadsheet and on the Ontomaton, a Google Spreadsheet plugin ²⁰ part of the ISA software suite, which allowed to query ontologies accessing the NCBO Bioportal ²¹, the EBI Ontology Lookup Service ²² and the LOD vocabulary service ²³. The NCBO Annotator ²⁴ service was also used in the first round of annotation, after having identified a subset of resources to query. All terms suggestions were reviewed prior to approval.

After having reviewed an earlier attempt to represent reporting guidelines with a purely RDF approach (MIM vocabulary) ²⁵, our choice to use JSON Schema and JSON-LD was guided by three main observations. First, JSON Schema and JSON are extremely popular formats for

developing web-oriented components. Second, a number of large scale biology related programs have adopted a data modeling approach rooted in JSON Schema technology. For instance, the Human Cell Atlas project ¹⁶ is developing metadata models relying on JSON Schema draft 7.0 (<https://github.com/HumanCellAtlas/metadata-schema>). Third, JSON Schema and JSON documents are widely supported, with dozens of libraries available for reading, writing, validating, parsing and rendering the information. While there is support to validate RDF graphs against a set of conditions (e.g., SHACL <http://datashapes.org/forms.html>, and Shex shape expressions <https://www.w3.org/2015/03/ShExValidata>, <https://github.com/CSIRO-enviro-informatics/shacl-form>), these technologies were less pervasive.

For the software implementation, we followed software engineering best practices, and Github ²⁶ was used to archive, version, release and document the code. Object orientation approach was used and Agile methodology applied, along with pair programming and systematic code review through a branching and pull request approach. Code quality was ensured through unit testing, as well integration testing. The GitHub repositories were set up to enable continuous integration using Travis CI (<https://travis-ci.com/auth>) and Coveralls (<https://coveralls.io/>) hooks, allowing building of the infrastructure on each commit and notification of the developers systematically on any critical failure. The documentation is available as readthedocs (<https://jsonldschema.readthedocs.io/>). It covers the entire set of components making up FAIRsharing JSON-LD Schema library, namely: (i) the JSON-LD Schema python module, which provides the functionality to deal with JSON Schemas accompanied by JSON-LD context files, allowing JSON Schemas for JSON-LD instances, (ii) the AngularJS web application JSON Schema *Documenter*, and (iii) the AngularJS web application JSON Schema *Compare and View* that supports visualisation of the comparison.

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Competing Interests

The authors have no competing interests. SAS is the Academic Editor of Scientific Data, and PRS is a member of its Senior Editorial Board.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: AGB, DB, PRS, SAS.; software-lead: AGB, DB; writing-original draft: SAS, PRS; writing-review and editing: AGB, DB.; funding acquisition: SAS, PRS.